

**JUSTIFICATION OF THE TECHNICAL CAPABILITIES OF A FOUR-
WHEEL TRACTOR WITH HIGH GROUND CLEARANCE**

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**ОБОСНОВАНИЕ ТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ ВОЗМОЖНОСТЕЙ
ЧЕТЫРЕХКОЛЕСНОГО ТРАКТОРА С ВЫСОКИМ ДОРОЖНЫМ
ПРОСВЕТОМ**

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Abstract: This study examines the technical capabilities of a four-wheeled cultivator tractor designed with high ground clearance, focusing on its suitability for agricultural operations in challenging terrains. High ground clearance enhances the tractor's ability to navigate uneven fields, minimize crop damage, and perform various tasks, including plowing, weeding, and seeding, without compromising efficiency. Key technical parameters such as engine power, maneuverability, and stability are analyzed to justify the tractor's effectiveness. The study highlights how this design improves productivity, reduces operational costs, and meets the evolving needs of modern agriculture, especially in areas with dense crops and uneven ground.

Key words: Four-wheeled cultivator tractor, high ground clearance, technical capabilities, crop protection, maneuverability, stability.

Аннотация: В данном исследовании рассматриваются технические возможности четырёхколёсного культиваторного трактора с высоким дорожным просветом, с акцентом на его пригодность для сельскохозяйственных работ в сложных условиях местности. Высокий дорожный просвет улучшает способность трактора передвигаться по неровным полям, минимизировать повреждение посевов и выполнять различные задачи, включая вспашку, прополку и посев, без снижения эффективности. Анализируются ключевые технические параметры, такие как мощность двигателя, маневренность и устойчивость, чтобы обосновать эффективность трактора. В исследовании подчеркивается, как эта конструкция повышает продуктивность, снижает операционные затраты и соответствует меняющимся требованиям современной сельскохозяйственной отрасли, особенно в районах с плотными посевами и неровным рельефом.

Ключевые слова: Четырёхколесный культиваторный трактор, высокий дорожный просвет, сельскохозяйственная техника, технические возможности, защита посевов, маневренность, устойчивость

Introduction

In modern agriculture, the demand for versatile and efficient machinery has grown

significantly as farmers seek solutions to optimize crop production across diverse terrains. The four-wheeled cultivator tractor with high ground clearance has emerged as a specialized machine addressing these needs. High ground clearance allows the tractor to operate effectively in dense and tall crops, as well as on uneven ground, minimizing the risk of crop damage and enabling seamless movement across various field conditions.

Basis of the cotton-growing tractor fleet of the Republic of Uzbekistan consists of universal-row crop tractors of 1.4 class, such as high-clearance 3-wheel TTZ-811 tractor (Figure 1, a) and medium clearance 4-wheel TTZ-810 tractor (Figure 1, b) [1]. As shown by researches carried out with respect of cultivating the cotton-plant more than 70 technologic operations, the share of 3-wheeled TTZ-811 tractors accounts for 17 operations, and share of 4-wheeled TTZ-810 – 22 tractor operations [2]. Moreover, the TTZ-811 tractor is mostly used for sowing and row-spacings cultivation of cotton crops (cultivation, cutting furrows, pest control, defoliation and desiccation) and crops associated to it, while the TTZ-810 tractor for presowing tillage, for harvesting and transport activities [1]. As a result of this distribution the volume of work, both tractors operate not loaded during the year. Replacing these two types of wheeled tractors with one highclearance 4-wheeled tractor significantly reduces the range of fleet and increases the annual load of universal-row crop tractor of 1.4 class, and finally, increases the efficiency of their applying.

Materials and methods

This study utilized a four-wheeled cultivator tractor with adjustable high ground clearance to assess its technical capabilities under various agricultural conditions. Key materials included a selection of agricultural fields with varying terrains and crop densities to simulate real-world conditions. The methodology involved a series of field tests to evaluate key parameters: ground clearance height, engine power, maneuverability, and stability. Many works have been devoted to improving the efficiency of using wheeled tractors in the field. The results of these researches made it possible to outline ways for increasing the traction and coupling properties, reduce

the technogenic influence on the soil of tractor movers, and improve the efficiency of using the machine-tractor units (MTU) [3].

Figure 1. Universal-row crop tractors of 1.4 class: (a) – tractor with 3K2 wheel arrangement; (b) – tractor with 4K2 wheel arrangement

Solution of issues the applying in cotton growing the high-clearance 4-wheeled tractors of new generation with high functional capability, adapted to loads of various types and sizes, with wide speed range of use for fulfilling the agrotechnological requirements of agricultural operations in various operating conditions, when aggregated with high-clearance of wide-mounted machine instruments (seeding and cultivating machines). It requires the increased traction potential, is actual task and needs to implement scientific-research and trial-design (experimental) activities [4].

Results and discussion

The field tests demonstrated that the four-wheeled cultivator tractor with high ground clearance showed enhanced adaptability and efficiency in challenging agricultural conditions. Results indicated that the high ground clearance minimized crop damage across varying crop heights, particularly in fields with dense and tall vegetation. In effort to evaluate the agrotechnical passability of wheeled tractors, there are several indicators [5]. One of them is the maneuverability (passability) margin,

which is ratio of the tangential traction force throughout the coupling to the soil to total sum of the rolling resistance forces and the traction force on the hook, i.e.

$$P = \frac{P_t}{P_r + P_h}, \quad (1)$$

where P_t – tangential force of traction throughout the coupling with soil, N; P_r – resistance force against the rolling, N; P_h – traction force on the hook, N. Tangential traction force in the traction with soil is determined on the basis of the below given formula:

$$P_t = \varphi_{\max} G_c \quad (2)$$

where $\varphi_{\max}$ – coefficient of wheel coupling with soil; G_c – coupling force, N. $G_c = m_c g$. The following are m_c – coupling weight of the tractor, kg; g – free fall acceleration, m/s^2 .

The relocation resistance force is determined according the formula as below given:

$$P_r = f_r G_t, \quad (3)$$

where f_r – relocation coefficient; G_t – gravity force of the tractor, N. In the event if $P_h=0$ the tangential force of tractor traction is performed only for solo run relocation of the tractor. Value $P \cong 1$ acknowledges, that tractor base on the coupling terms and conditions with supporting basis within the framework of agrotechnical requirements (upon allowed value of skidding) ensure normal aggretaging of agrocltural machine with necessary (including maximum) traction forcening.

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Main activities focused on improving the traction and coupling indicators of wheeled agricultural tractors are the following:

- tire Optimization and Selection
- weight Distribution and Ballasting
- improving Wheel and Axle Design
- using the all tractor wheels as leading;
- rational distribution along with the axes of operational mass of the unit etc.

Adjustable agrotechnical portal-type clearance of the lower part of the front axle values A increments of 100 mm, respectively 650, 750, 850 mm, therefore the angles of rotation of the front wheels are $\beta_i=55^\circ$ ба $\beta_i=37^\circ$. Adjustable agrotechnical clearance the front of axle the rut is regulated, is adjusted accordingly to 1200-1800 mm.

Considering this circumstance, at the Scientific-Research Institute of Agricultural Mechanization (SRIAM) on the basis of TTZ-1032, an experimental high-clearance universal-row crop tractor with all leading wheels was developed, i.e. with 4K2 wheel arrangement (Figure 2) for working at cotton-plants growing and its trial (experimental) sample was manufactured [6, 7].

Figure 2. Front view of the experimental 4K2 wheel configuration tractor equipped with an adjustable agro technical clearance front axle.

The main design parameters and technical characteristics of trial sample of the cotton-growing high clearance experimental tractor with 4K2 wheel arrangement were

determined during a technical examination using well-known methods and equipment of the Center for Certification and Testing of Agricultural Machinery and Technology (CTMT), and they are given in table 1.

According to the results of technical expertise and field tests of a prototype of high-clearance 4K2 tractor for cotton-plant growing, it was established that operating weight of the tractor is 4506 kg, and the tractor corresponds to a pull class of 1.4 (14 kN).

Technical characteristics of trial (experimental) tractor

Table 1.

№	Name and unit of measurement the parameters	Designation	Value of parameters
1	Wheel arrangement		4K2
2	Fixed steep load, N		21974
3	Agrotechnical clearance (100 mm step by step), mm,	<i>A</i>	650, 750, 850
4	Rut, mm:		
	– of the front wheels – of the rear part wheels	<i>B₁</i>	1820
	– of the front wheels – of the rear part wheels	<i>B₂</i>	1770
5	Longitudinal base, mm	<i>L</i>	2585
6	Type and sizes of tires:		
	– of the front wheels – of the rear part wheels		7,5-20
	– of the rear wheels – of the rear part wheels		15,5-38
7	Static radius of wheels, mm:		
	– of the front wheels – of the rear part wheels	<i>r_{st}</i>	435
	– of the rear wheels – of the rear part wheels		730

Conclusion

In conclusion, the four-wheeled cultivator tractor with high ground clearance presents significant advantages for modern agricultural practices, particularly in challenging terrains characterized by uneven surfaces and dense crop conditions.

Implemented researches has shown that applying the universal-row crop tractor on all operations provided by the technological map for performing with traction class tractor of 1.4 (14 kN) ensures its year-round load and, thus, significantly improves its performance indicators and economic efficiency as well. The weight distribution of perspective four-wheeled universal-row crop tractor onto four wheels and fully drive reduces the negative impact on soil in comparison with three-wheeled tractor and allows to aggregate machines having enlarge drow-spacings.

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